

Endocrown: A Unique Way of Restoration

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Received on: 07 September 2024; Accepted on: 27 September 2024; Published on : 20 October 2024

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Abstract

The restoration of endodontically treated molar teeth with more than one cusp missing and thin remaining walls is challenging for the general practitioner. Teeth that undergo root canal therapy require some form of restoration to enable them to be functional again. Minimally invasive preparation to preserve maximum amount of tooth structure is considered to be the standard goal for restoring teeth. Endocrowns represent a simple, conservative, and esthetic alternative to conventional crowns. Endocrown restoration is more conservative than traditional post and core system and uses the adhesive resin with monoblock technique. These restorations are self-cleansing, prevent interferences with periodontal tissues due to the supragingival margins, maintain natural contact and increase longevity of the tooth. The rationale of this technique is to use the surface area available in the pulp chamber to achieve stability and retention through adhesive techniques. Endocrown is a feasible option for the restoration of extensively damaged posterior tooth after endodontic treatment. This case report emphasizes on endodontically treated mandibular molar requiring post endodontic prosthetic rehabilitation with Endocrown.

Keywords: Endocrown, Endodontically treated tooth, monoblock, minimally invasive dentistry.

Introduction

The success & failure of endodontically treated tooth depend upon its treatment quality & appropriate coronal restoration to maintain tooth form, function & esthetics.

The best restoration method for endodontically treated teeth has been debated extensively in the literature. However, significant advancement in the past twenty years emphasise the preservation of tooth structure.¹

A tooth after endodontic treatment require more complex restoration than normal tooth, because lot of loss of tooth structure reduces its fracture resistance, mechanical properties thus affecting the tooth long term survival rate.²

With the advancement of adhesive technique an increased focus on minimally invasive procedure, restorative alternate for posterior endodontically treated teeth such as Endocrown are now available. Piss developed the technique for endocrown restorations in 1995 but the term Endocrown was coined by Bindl & Mormann in 1999.³

An Endodontic crown or endocrown restoration is more conservative than traditional post and core system and uses the adhesive resin with monoblock techni-

que. Endocrown restoration is partial or full coverage of coronal portion of an endodontically treated teeth made up of mainly all ceramic material & take advantage of the pulp chamber and possibly the root canal entrances to increase the adhesive surface area.⁴

Indications

Successfully root canal treated molar.
Excessive loss of coronal dentinal tissue and limited interocclusal space.
Teeth with short clinical crowns.
Calcified, curved or short root canals that make post application impossible.

Contraindications

Para functional habits
Depth of pulp chamber less than 3 mm.
Cervical margin less than 2 mm wide.
If adhesion process cannot be assured.

Case Report

A 23-year-old male reported to the department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics in Chandra dental college and Hospital, Barabanki with the chief com-

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How to cite this article: Singh et al. - Endocrown: A Unique Way of Restoration
HTAJOCD 2024

plaint of intermittent pain in the lower right back tooth region of jaw since two months. The medical history was non-contributory. On the clinical examination, tooth # 47 had occlusal caries with involvement of central ridge (Fig.1). Tooth was sensitive to percussion & pulp vitality test was positive.

On the radiographic examination, the tooth # 47 had deep caries approaching the pulp chamber and also widening of periodontal ligament space. The patient had an acceptable oral hygiene & a favorable occlusion.

Endocrown restoration was recommended for the present case because of the decreased amount of remaining tooth structure and the thickness of the walls. It was decided to perform, root canal treatment followed by endocrown restoration according to minimal invasive principle. Patient was informed about the treatment plan and informed consent was taken. The tooth # 47 was anesthetized using a local anesthetic (2% lignocaine with 1:100,000 epinephrine) solution by way of inferior alveolar nerve block of the right side of the jaw. Under rubber dam, access cavity preparation was done with endo access bur. Working length was determined with the help of 21 mm #10 K file (Fig.2).

After working length determination, all the canals were biomechanically prepared using the crown down technique with the help of rotary NiTi file system. During biomechanical preparation, NaOCl and EDTA were used as irrigating solution to remove the necrosed pulp tissue & debris from the root canal. After completion of biomechanical preparation of root canal & selection of master gutta percha cones (fig.3), drying the canal using sterile paper points, calcium hydroxide as intracanal medicament was placed in the canals & cavity was sealed with temporary restoration (cavit). Patient was recalled after one week. In second visit, tooth was asymptomatic. Intracanal medicament was removed using hand instrumentation (H-files) and copious irrigation of root canal was done with irrigating solution. The root canal was dried with sterile paper points & obturated with master gutta percha cones & bioceramic sealer. The access cavity was sealed with temporary restorative material & post operative radiograph was taken to verify the quality of obturation (Fig. 4)

Fig.1 Preoperative Clinical Photograph

Fig. 2 Working length Radiograph

Fig. 3 Master Cone Radiograph

Fig. 4 Post Obturation radiograph

The preparation for the endo-crown is different from the conventional full coverage crown. Before starting the procedure, first we do the shade selection in day light. The cervical margin has to be supragingival in a circumferential manner and width of enamel margin less than 2 mm have to be eliminated. A cervical butt joint i.e. 90° was created. The preparation consisted in reducing the occlusal surface height at least 2 mm in the axial direction. To achieve occlusal reduction, one approach is to drill 2 mm guide groove followed by a wheel bur was oriented along the long axis of the tooth & parallel to the occlusal plane. To get a flat surface in the form of a butt joint. The preparation of pulp chamber involves removing the undercuts in the access cavity, a cylindrical-conical bur with a occlusal taper of 7° was used to make the

continuous coronal pulp chamber & endodontic access cavity. The bur was orientated along the long axis of the tooth, the preparation was done without too much pressure and without touching the pulpal floor to create smooth taper walls.

The depth of the pulp chamber must be at least 3 mm. Remove the gutta-percha upto a depth of 2 mm to obtain a saddle anatomy of the floor, which provide more stability. (Fig.5). After evaluating the entire cavity and the interocclusal space, the impression of the tooth was taken by double impression technique using additional silicone impression material. After visualization and analysis of the quality of the impression, we sent the impression to the laboratory (Fig.6). All ceramic endocrown was fabricated in the laboratory (Fig.7) and was positioned on the master cast (Fig.8). Then we made a try-in of the endocrown (#47) and checked occlusion, internal, and proximal adjustments.

A thin layer of a dual polymerizing resin was applied to the prosthetic endocrown and then was inserted into the prepared tooth and polymerized at intervals of 5 seconds, making it easy to remove excess cement.

After that, it was polymerized for 60 seconds on all surfaces. The restoration was examined for any occlusal interference (Fig.9).

Post operative clinical photograph was taken to ensure complete seating of endocrown & there is no residual cement (Fig.10)

Fig. 5 Tooth Preparation (#47) for Endocrown

Fig. 6 Impression for Preparation

Fig. 7 Fabricated Endocrown

Fig. 8 Endocrown on the Master Cast

Fig. 9 Placement of Endocrown with dual cure resin cement

Fig. 10 Post-Operative Clinical Photograph

Discussion

The design of the restorative treatment of molars with a large coronal destruction, a clinical challenge, requires careful planning. That is why the dentist has to decide for the best treatment option to ensure an efficient treatment providing clinical longevity of molars.⁵ The objective of the preparation is to get a wide and stable surface resisting the compressive stresses that are frequent in molars. The prepared surface is parallel to the occlusal plane to provide stress resistance along the major axis of the tooth. The stress levels in teeth with endocrowns were lower than in teeth with prosthetic crowns.⁶ Due to the development of adhesive cementation systems, the need for microinvasive preparation for crown are in great demand. The pulpal chamber cavity also provides retention and stability. Trapezoidal shape of pulp chamber in mandibular molars and triangular shape of pulp chamber in maxillary molars increase the restoration's stability and additional preparation is not needed.⁷

Bernhart et al., concluded that endocrowns “represent a very promising treatment alternative for endodontically treated molars.” This anatomy, along with the adhesive qualities of the bonding material, makes it unessential to attempt further use of post-involving root canals. In fact, the root canals do not need any specific shape; therefore, they are not fragilized by the drilling and they will not receive the stresses associated with the use of post.⁸

Biacchi and Basting concluded that endocrowns were more resistant to compressive forces than conventional crowns. The compressive stresses are reduced, being distributed over the cervical butt joint and the walls of the pulp chamber.⁹

The long-term success of restoration of endodontically treated teeth with endocrown depends on careful case selection & thorough implementation of the adhesive procedure.

Conclusion

The preparation for endocrowns is simple and can be achieved quickly. Root canals are not engaged in the process and the procedure is less traumatic than tooth preparation for post & core restoration. The supragingival position of the cervical margin protects the marginal periodontium, facilitates impression taking and preserves the solid substance of the remaining tooth. Masticatory forces are dispersed over the cervical butt joint (compression) and axial walls (shear force), thus moderating the load on the pulpal floor. Although the use of endocrown is commonly for molars further research is needed to determine their suitability for premolars & anteriors.

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